

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Failure of vein grafts and the impact on cardiovascular health after coronary artery bypass surgery

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

Organisation
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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

Failure of Vein Grafts and the Impact on Cardiovascular Health after Coronary Artery Bypass Surgery.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

Prospective in-vivo Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Computed Tomography (CT) imaging study on saphenous vein graft failure and wider implications of coronary artery bypass graft surgery.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

The data will be quantitative, generated from: 1. in vivo PET-CT and CT images and the subsequent analysis of these; 2. medical records, electronic health records, and clinical measurements.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

We plan to collect new data for this proposal. PET-CT images will be taken in different imaging facilities across the UK and then analysed. We will gather clinical data through interviews, echocardiography, electrocardiography, and by accessing medical records from NHS Lothian's secure data environment. Before being inputted into case reports, this data will be anonymised and securely stored.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Imaging data: PET and CT scans may require ~ 5TB of data storage.

Each participant's Case Report Form, including demographic information, previous medical conditions, and test results, may require < 100MB

Wherever possible, open-source standard formats will be used. If not possible, standard file formats in research will be utilised to enable data sharing and maintain long-term validity. Digital data will be recorded on Microsoft Office Word and Excel files and PDFs. Image analysis for all images will be performed using the FusionQuant software (Cedars Sinai Hospital, Los Angeles). Mean and maximum standardised uptake values (SUV) for radiotracer uptake will be measured and target to background ratios (TBR) will be calculated.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Patient data will be anonymised and recorded in case report forms. The paper case report forms will be stored in locked filing cabinets within the local facility with restricted access. Later, the data from the case reports will be entered into a Microsoft Excel database. All electronic data will be stored and backed up daily using password-protected local network storage, which can only be accessed with two-factor authentication. We will use Common Data Elements from the NIH Common Data Elements Repository for data collection and the Medical Imaging and Data Resource Center (MIDRC) Commons dictionary for imaging data. Data standards expected to be used; [DICOM](#) (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine).

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

To enhance discoverability, aggregations and analysis of content in different websites and services, it is essential that the metadata served by these resources is consistently structured. Descriptive metadata will be produced at the time of publication/presentation of research outputs. This will include details of the methodology used to obtain and subsequently analyse our data; to allow other researchers to perform related analysis on subsequent studies. The project will follow UK Data Service guidelines for describing quantitative data. Documentation will be developed carefully to ensure it provides sufficient information to understand the content without providing information that may be used to re-identify individuals.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All relevant research outputs, including appropriate metadata, will be retained for a minimum of 10 years in accordance with the BBSRC Statement on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice. Only anonymised data will be suitable for sharing within the team and with external researchers.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

Any data that can be shared publicly will be stored in existing public databases. Due to their large size, the datasets might be spread in different repositories, such as [Zenodo](#), UK Data Service, and institutional open repositories.

All repositories will provide a digital object identifier (DOI), which can be used by anyone who cites this data in the future. Additionally, any academic conference presentations or scientific publications that utilise this data will provide information about data sharing for this study.

(Q10) When will data be available?

Data will be made accessible to others in a timely manner. Data will be released at the same time as any published outputs which are underpinned by the data or by 1 year from the end of the project at the latest.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

To ensure that the data is easily accessible and discoverable in the long term, it will be submitted along with detailed metadata. The repositories will provide a digital object identifier (DOI), which can be used by anyone who cites this data in the future. Additionally, any academic conference presentations or scientific publications that utilise this data will provide information about data sharing for this study.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

To enable easy interpretation of the dataset, it will be thoroughly documented with all necessary information for others to reuse the data. It will also be published under Creative Commons Attribution Licence conditions and with sufficient metadata to describe its origin and use.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

Participants in the research studies will be asked for their consent before taking part. The consent forms will make it clear that participants agree to share anonymised data with our research partners. The data will be shared promptly and will be made public through oral and poster presentations, as well as research paper publications.

(Q14) Secondary use

Due to its strong association with clinical outcomes, graft status may be useful as a surrogate outcome in clinical trials of patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting. Insights will be developed based on this information and this will help identify key drivers of development and innovation in this area.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

The policies and standards of participating institutions and ethical committees for implementing and maintaining an effective information security management system will be followed. Data will be stored on secure systems, and access will be restricted to the research team. The University has ISO 27001 certification.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

To protect the privacy of our study participants and keep the data secure, we will use encryption protocols for data in transit and storage, implement access controls, and conduct regular backups and disaster recovery plans. Our physical security measures include secure storage facilities. Personnel with data access will receive training and awareness programs, and we will perform regular audits to ensure compliance with consent and security conditions. Through these measures, we believe we can effectively manage the risks to the confidentiality and security of the information.

(Q17) Capabilities

No additional costs are expected beyond those included in the project application to ensure ongoing access to all data and software. The organisation's data manager will assist with data management requirements throughout the research data lifecycle.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

The data management plan is a living document that will be updated as needed throughout the project. The principal investigator is primarily responsible for it, and the organisational data manager is responsible for revising and providing feedback when necessary.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University has participated in Green Impact since 2009/2010 as part of our behaviour change strategy to reduce our carbon emissions. We have saved 3 million kg of CO₂ through the staff sustainability projects. The University has also joined the UN Race to Zero Campaign, an alliance committed to achieving net-zero carbon emissions by 2050 at the latest.

(Q20) Responsibilities

The principal investigator is primarily accountable for research data management. During the research process, researchers are responsible for adhering to legal requirements such as Data Protection and creating metadata and other documentation that enables data to be discoverable, understandable, and reusable.

After the deposit of data with a repository, the repository is responsible for the ongoing management of that data in accordance with legal, technical and other requirements.

The University will be responsible for providing a Research Data Management service to include training, advice, guidance and data curation.